

8T – Matric Tensor Fluctuations and the Birth of Universes

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T framework it is possible to construct the process in which new universe may arise from distinct pre-existing varying manifold with (3,1) signature. The process of birth is due to a matric tensor variations. At certain instances there could be a segment matric tensor to experience an arbitrary amount of curvature causing to depart from the original manifold, this segment is assumed infinitesimally small, and now at point a curvature on it will appear it will be flattened by other infinite uncompact manifolds.

Introduction

The new 8T framework is revolving around a Variational Lorentz manifolds, which assumed stationary. Using the main equation of the theory and the two conditions specified in equations (1.1) it is possible to describe the so-called "dark energy". The reason for this can be derived from a variation of equation one, by assuming that there are infinite amount of manifolds all demanded to be stationary, that is described by equation (1.1)

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad , \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.21)$$

The metric tensor experiences arbitrary variations that vanish into matter. We describe the process of arbitrary variations vanishing into matter in the thesis, by the variation of the Dirac Delta function.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta g &\neq 0 & \text{at} & & t &= Q(t) \\ \delta g &= 0 & \text{at} & & t &= Q(t + \Delta t) \end{aligned}$$

Those arbitrary variations vanish in even number, as proven by the thesis. The term describing those is given by equation (1):

$$\begin{aligned} \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots &= \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \\ \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

There is always a chance net curvature will appear at later continuation of time. That is bosonic fields given by the primordial coupling series:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta g &= 0 & \text{at} & & t &= Q(t + \Delta t) \\ \delta g &\neq 0 & \text{at} & & t_2 &= Q(t + \Delta t + \Delta t) \\ \Delta t &\rightarrow 0 \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the amount of net curvature is either prime or one:

$$\delta g = N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \geq 0$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.3}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.31}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Now that we presented the 8T foundation, we can visualize the birth of new universe. By assuming a segment of the metric tensor to experience a certain amount of curvature it could lead to a departing from the original manifold. One can try to put it in visual means. This idea is synonymous with the vacuum fluctuations in QFT.

The main point of this short essay is that the net curvature led to a departing from the original metric tensor to a new entity. The outer shell of this new manifold will accelerate due to other manifolds wrapping around it given by equation (1.2). That is in agreement with QFT prediction of infinite universes. The entire evolution of the universes from singularity to complete flatness is given by the main equation (1). The stage and actual flattening moment is different in each manifold. That is an elegant way to eliminate the question – why 13.7B years?

References

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